

Deng entropy: a generalized Shannon entropy to measure uncertainty

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Abstract

Shannon entropy is an efficient tool to measure uncertain information. However, it cannot handle the more uncertain situation when the uncertainty is represented by basic probability assignment (BPA), instead of probability distribution, under the framework of Dempster Shafer evidence theory. To address this issue, a new entropy, named as Deng entropy, is proposed. The proposed Deng entropy is the generalization of Shannon entropy. If uncertain information is represented by probability distribution, the uncertain degree measured by Deng entropy is the same as that of Shannon's entropy. Some numerical examples are illustrated to show the efficiency of Deng entropy.

Keywords: Uncertainty measure, Entropy, Deng entropy, Shannon entropy, Dempster-Shafer evidence theory

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1. Introduction

Uncertainty is ubiquitous in nature. How to measure the uncertainty has attracted much attention [1, 2]. Various categorizations exist to accommodate different kinds of uncertainties. Numerous uncertainty theories have been developed, such as probability theory [3], fuzzy set theory [4], possibility theory [5], Dempster-Shafer evidence theory [6, 7], rough sets [8], DSmT [9, 10], generalized evidence theory [11] and D numbers [12, 13, 14, 15].

Since firstly proposed by Clausius in 1865 for thermodynamics [16], the study of uncertainty and entropy attracts great interests and various types of entropies are developed, such as information entropy [17], Tsallis entropy [18], nonadditive entropy [19, 20, 21]. Information entropy [17], derived from the Boltzmann-Gibbs (BG) entropy [22] in thermodynamics and statistical mechanics, has been an indicator to measure aleatoric uncertainty which is associated with the probability density function (PDF).

For the aleatoric uncertain information expressed by PDF, information entropy proposed by Shannon [17] is a good measure. However, with respect to other uncertain information including epistemic, irreducible, reducible and inferential uncertainty, classical information entropy is invalid. In this paper, one of these uncertainties, epistemic uncertainty, is taken into consideration. Dempster-Shafer theory evidence theory [6, 7] is mainly proposed to handle such uncertainty. In Dempster-Shafer evidence theory, the epistemic uncertainty simultaneously contains nonspecificity and discord [23] which are coexisting in a basic probability assignment function (BPA). Several un-

certainty measures, such as AU [24, 25], AM [23], have been proposed to quantify such uncertainty in Dempster-Shafer theory. What's more, five axiomatic requirements have been further built in order to develop a justifiable measure. These five axiomatic requirements are range, probabilistic consistency, set consistency, additivity, subadditivity, respectively [26]. However, existing methods are not efficient to measure uncertain degree of BPA. To address this issue, a new entropy, named as Deng entropy, is proposed in this paper.

The paper is organized as follows. The preliminaries Dempster-Shafer evidence theory and entropy are briefly introduced in Section 2. Section 3 presents Deng entropy. Some numerical examples are illustrated in Section 4 to show the efficiency of Deng entropy. Finally, this paper is concluded in Section 5.

2. Preliminaries

In this section, some preliminaries are briefly introduced.

2.1. Dempster-Shafer evidence theory

Dempster-Shafer theory (short for D-S theory), also called belief function theory, as introduced by Dempster[6] and then developed by Shafer[7], has emerged from their works on statistical inference and uncertain reasoning. This theory is widely applied to uncertainty modeling [27, 28], decision making [29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37]and information fusion [38, 39] and uncertain information processing [40]. D-S theory mainly focus on the epis-

temic uncertainty, but it is also valid for aleatoric uncertainty. It has many merits by contrast probability theory. First, D-S theory can handle more uncertainty in real world. In contrast to the probability theory in which probability masses can be only assigned to singleton subsets, in D-S theory the belief can be assigned to both singletons and compound sets. Second, in D-S theory, prior distribution is not needed before the combination of information from individual information sources. Third, D-S theory allows one to specify a degree of ignorance in some situations instead of being forced to be assigned for probabilities. Some basic concepts in D-S theory are introduced.

Let X be a set of mutually exclusive and collectively exhaustive events, indicated by

$$X = \{\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_i, \dots, \theta_{|X|}\} \quad (1)$$

where set X is called a frame of discernment. The power set of X is indicated by 2^X , namely

$$2^X = \{\emptyset, \{\theta_1\}, \dots, \{\theta_{|X|}\}, \{\theta_1, \theta_2\}, \dots, \{\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_i\}, \dots, X\} \quad (2)$$

For a frame of discernment $X = \{\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{|X|}\}$, a mass function is a mapping m from 2^X to $[0, 1]$, formally defined by:

$$m : 2^X \rightarrow [0, 1] \quad (3)$$

which satisfies the following condition:

$$m(\emptyset) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{A \in 2^X} m(A) = 1 \quad (4)$$

In D-S theory, a mass function is also called a basic probability assignment (BPA). Assume there are two BPAs indicated by m_1 and m_2 , the Dempster's rule of combination is used to combine them as follows:

$$m(A) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{1-K} \sum_{B \cap C = A} m_1(B)m_2(C), & A \neq \emptyset; \\ 0, & A = \emptyset. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

with

$$K = \sum_{B \cap C = \emptyset} m_1(B)m_2(C) \quad (6)$$

Note that the Dempster's rule of combination is only applicable to such two BPAs which satisfy the condition $K < 1$.

D-S theory has more advantages in handling uncertainty compared with classical probability theory. When information is adequate, probability theory is effective to handle that situation. However, when information is not adequate, probability theory is invalid to such uncertain situation. Here is an example.

As shown in Figure 1, assume there are two boxes. There are red balls in the left box, and green balls in the right box. The number of balls in each box is unknown. Now, a person is assigned to pick a ball from these two boxes. We know that he chooses the left box with a probability $P1 = 0.6$, and chooses the right box with a probability $P2 = 0.4$. Based on probability theory, it can be obtained that the probability of picking a red ball is 0.6, the probability of picking a green ball is 0.4, namely $p(R) = 0.6$, $p(G) = 0.4$.

Now, let us change the configuration, as shown in Figure 2. In the left box, there are still only red balls. But in the right box, there are not only red balls

Figure 1: A game of picking ball which can be handled by probability theory

but also green balls. In accord with above, the exact number of balls in each box is still unknown, and the ratio of them are completely unknown. This person also has 0.6 probability to choose the left box and 0.4 probability to choose the right box. The question is how possible that a red ball is picked. Obviously, in this case due to lack of adequate information, $p(R)$ and $p(G)$ cannot be obtained. Facing the situation of inadequate information, probability theory is incapable. However, if using D-S theory to analyze this problem, we can obtain a BPA that $m(R) = 0.6$ and $m(R, G) = 0.4$, which means the probability of red ball being picked is 0.6 and the probability of red ball or green ball being picked is 0.4. In the framework of D-S theory, the uncertainty has been expressed more effective. D-S theory has more ability to express uncertain information than probability theory.

Figure 2: A game of picking ball where probability theory is unable but D-S theory is able to handle

2.2. Existing entropy and open issue

Entropy is associated with uncertainty, and it has been a measure of uncertainty and disorder. The concept of entropy is derived from physics [16]. In thermodynamics and statistical mechanics, the entropy often refers to Boltzmann-Gibbs entropy [22]. According to Boltzmann's H theorem, the Boltzmann-Gibbs (BG) entropy of an isolated system S_{BG} is obtained in terms of the probabilities associated the distinct microscopic states available to the system given the macroscopic constraints, which has the following form

$$S_{BG} = -k \sum_{i=1}^W p_i \ln p_i \quad (7)$$

where k is the Boltzmann constant, W is the amount of distinct microscopic states available to the isolated system, p_i is the probability of microscopic state i satisfying $\sum_{i=1}^W p_i = 1$. Equal probabilities, i.e. $\forall i, p_i = 1/W$, is a

particular situation. In that situation, BG entropy has the following form

$$S_{BG} = k \ln W \quad (8)$$

In information theory, Shannon entropy [17] is often used to measure the information volume of a system or a process, and quantify the expected value of the information contained in a message. Information entropy, denoted as H , has a similar form with BS entropy

$$H = - \sum_{i=1}^N p_i \log_b p_i \quad (9)$$

where N is the amount of basic states in a state space, p_i is the probability of state i appears satisfying $\sum_{i=1}^W p_i = 1$, b is base of logarithm. When $b = 2$, the unit of information entropy is bit. If each state equally appears, the quantity of H has this form

$$H = \log_2 N \quad (10)$$

In information theory, quantities of H play a central role as measures of information, choice and uncertainty. For example, the Shannon entropy of the game shown in Figure 1 is $H = 0.6 \times \log_2 0.6 + 0.4 \times \log_2 0.4 = 0.9710$. But, it is worthy to notice that the uncertainty of this game shown in Figure 2 cannot be calculated by using the Shannon entropy.

According to mentioned above, no matter the BG entropy or the information entropy, the quantity of entropy is always associated with the amount of states in a system. Especially, for the case of equal probabilities, the en-

entropy or the uncertainty of a system is a function of the quantity of states. Moreover, in that particular case, the entropy is the maximum.

3. Deng entropy

With the range of uncertainty mentioned above, Deng entropy can be presented as follows

$$E_d = - \sum_i m(F_i) \log \frac{m(F_i)}{2^{|F_i|} - 1} \quad (11)$$

where, F_i is a proposition in mass function m , and $|F_i|$ is the cardinality of F_i . As shown in the above definition, Deng entropy, formally, is similar with the classical Shannon entropy, but the belief for each proposition F_i is divided by a term $(2^{|F_i|} - 1)$ which represents the potential number of states in F_i (of course, the empty set is not included).

Specially, Deng entropy can definitely degenerate to the Shannon entropy if the belief is only assigned to single elements. Namely,

$$E_d = - \sum_i m(\theta_i) \log \frac{m(\theta_i)}{2^{|\theta_i|} - 1} = - \sum_i m(\theta_i) \log m(\theta_i)$$

4. Numerical examples and discussions

In the section, a lot of examples are given to show the effectiveness of Deng entropy.

Example 1. Assume there is a mass function $m(a) = 1$, the associated Shannon entropy H and Deng entropy E_d are calculated as follows.

$$H = 1 \times \log 1 = 0$$

$$E_d = 1 \times \log \frac{1}{2^1 - 1} = 0$$

Example 2. Given a frame of discernment $X = \{a, b, c\}$, for a mass function $m(a) = m(b) = m(c) = 1/3$, the associated Shannon entropy H and Deng entropy E_d are

$$H = -\frac{1}{3} \times \log \frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{3} \times \log \frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{3} \times \log \frac{1}{3} = 1.5850$$

$$E_d = -\frac{1}{3} \times \log \frac{1/3}{2^1 - 1} - \frac{1}{3} \times \log \frac{1/3}{2^1 - 1} - \frac{1}{3} \times \log \frac{1/3}{2^1 - 1} = 1.5850$$

Clearly, Example 1 and 2 have shown that the results of Shannon entropy and Deng entropy are identical when the belief is only assigned on single elements.

Example 3. Given a frame of discernment $X = \{a, b, c\}$, for a mass function $m(a, b, c) = 1$,

$$E_d = -1 \times \log \frac{1}{2^3 - 1} = 2.8074$$

For another mass function $m(a) = m(b) = m(c) = m(a, b) = m(a, c) = m(b, c) = m(a, b, c) = 1/7$,

$$E_d = -\frac{1}{7} \times \log \frac{1/7}{2^1 - 1} - \frac{1}{7} \times \log \frac{1/7}{2^1 - 1} - \frac{1}{7} \times \log \frac{1/7}{2^1 - 1} - \frac{1}{7} \times \log \frac{1/7}{2^2 - 1} - \frac{1}{7} \times \log \frac{1/7}{2^2 - 1} - \frac{1}{7} \times \log \frac{1/7}{2^2 - 1} - \frac{1}{7} \times \log \frac{1/7}{2^3 - 1} = 3.8877$$

Example 4. Given a frame of discernment $X = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_N\}$, let us consider three special cases of mass functions as follows.

- $m_1(F_i) = m_1(F_j)$ and $\sum_i m_1(F_i) = 1$, $\forall F_i, F_j \subseteq X$, $F_i, F_j \neq \emptyset$.
- $m_2(X) = 1$.
- $m_3(a_1) = m_3(a_2) = \dots = m_3(a_N) = 1/N$.

Their associated Deng entropies change with N , as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Deng entropy as a function of the size of frame of discernment in three types of mass functions

Example 5. Given a frame of discernment X with 15 elements which are denoted as element 1, element 2, etc. A mass function is shown as follows.

$$m(\{3, 4, 5\}) = 0.05, m(\{6\}) = 0.05, m(A) = 0.8, m(X) = 0.1$$

Table 1 lists various Deng entropies when A changes, which is graphically shown in Figure 4. The results shows that the entropy of m increases monotonously with the rise of the size of subset A . It is rational that the entropy increases when the uncertainty involving a mass function increases.

Table 1: Deng entropy when A changes

Cases	Deng entropy
$A = \{1\}$	1.8454
$A = \{1, 2\}$	2.7242
$A = \{1, 2, 3\}$	3.4021
$A = \{1, \dots, 4\}$	4.0118
$A = \{1, \dots, 5\}$	4.5925
$A = \{1, \dots, 6\}$	5.1599
$A = \{1, \dots, 7\}$	5.7207
$A = \{1, \dots, 8\}$	6.2784
$A = \{1, \dots, 9\}$	6.8345
$A = \{1, \dots, 10\}$	7.3898
$A = \{1, \dots, 11\}$	7.9447
$A = \{1, \dots, 12\}$	8.4994
$A = \{1, \dots, 13\}$	9.0540
$A = \{1, \dots, 14\}$	9.6086

Figure 4: Deng entropy as a function of the size of A

5. Conclusion

Dempster Shafer evidence theory has widely used in many applications due to its advantages to handle the aleatoric and epistemic uncertainty. However, how to measure uncertain degree in evidence theory is still an open issue. The main contribution of this paper is that a new entropy, named as Deng entropy, is presented. Deng entropy is the generalization of Shannon entropy. In the case when the BPA is degenerated as probability, Deng entropy is degenerated as Shannon entropy. However, Numerical examples are illustrated to show the efficiency of Deng entropy. Some properties of Deng entropy are discussed. The new entropy provides a promising way to measure uncertain degree. One of the ongoing works is to present the cross entropy of BPA, which can be easily derived.

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